

MASTER 1ST OPEN CALL: EXECUTION PERIOD KICK-OFF

In the beginning of 2024, the MASTER project launched its 1st Open Call, inviting extended reality (XR) technology developers, research institutes specialising in XR, and educational institutions from EU Member States, associated overseas countries and territories, and third countries linked to Horizon Europe.

Applicants were tasked with addressing specific challenges and submitting their proposals for evaluation. Following a rigorous assessment process involving both internal and external reviewers, 17 projects were selected, having met all required criteria.

The execution period for these projects commenced in December 2024 and will continue until August 2025. During this time, the 17 selected projects will:

- Receive financial support of up to €150,000 to develop their XR solutions.
- Integrate their technologies into the MASTER platform, ensuring seamless compatibility with its ecosystem.
- Benefit from technical and business support provided by the MASTER consortium to enhance their solutions and prepare them for practical use.
- Utilise MASTER platform tools, supported by VIRTUALWARE licenses and technical assistance.
- Explore potential commercialisation opportunities with VIRTUALWARE following the project's conclusion.

During the execution period, the projects will develop the technologies and functionalities that will be integrated in the platform and tested with a wide range of end users.

Advancing Industry Training Needs

This Open Call forms part of the MASTER project's broader mission to create a comprehensive library of XR solutions tailored to the challenges of robotics and manufacturing training. These solutions will be incorporated into the MASTER XR platform, making it an indispensable tool for industry-focused education and training.

Stay Updated

Progress updates on the selected projects will be shared regularly via the [MASTER project's website](#) and its LinkedIn channel.

About the MASTER Project

The MASTER project ("Manufacturing Education and Training through XR") is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative dedicated to advancing robotics training in manufacturing through the use of Extended Reality

technologies. By developing an open XR platform, MASTER aims to provide safe, adaptable robotic environments featuring advanced interaction mechanisms. Ultimately, the project seeks to empower non-expert programmers to create and manage XR educational content, contributing to a more skilled and technologically adept workforce.

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